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"We Had to Adopt as Singles": Power Relations and Resistance in Same-Sex Couples Seeking Adoption

Abstract

The study aimed to understand how LGBTQIA+ families seeking to become parents through adoption construct their subjectivities amid power and resistance relationships within the existing regulatory and cultural framework. Using a qualitative approach, in-depth interviews were conducted with LGBTQIA+ families and state officials, both individually and in groups, to explore their experiences and perceptions. Critical Discourse Analysis was used to understand how discursive practices shape the social context and subjectivities. The results reveal that the adoption process in Chile is heavily regulated by norms that favor the formation of heteronormative families, with legislation prioritizing married couples and relegating LGBTQIA+ families to a lower priority. Despite being recognized for their openness to adopting children with special needs or older children, LGBTQIA+ families face barriers and discrimination, highlighting a form of control that, although seemingly inclusive, perpetuates the marginalization of these families. The study emphasizes how superficial inclusion and normative regulation reinforce structural inequalities, underscoring the need for a critical examination of policies to promote social justice.

Keywords: Gender Equality; Adoption; Public Policy; Sexual Diversity; Chile

Introduction

The concept of family has evolved significantly, reflecting profound changes in social, cultural, and legal spheres. Traditionally understood as a unit composed of a father, mother, and children, the definition of family has expanded to include diverse configurations such as single-parent, blended, and same-sex families, among others (Piedra Guillén 2013). In this context, the family emerges as a central social institution in social organization, where powers, hierarchies, and values derived from gender differences are manifested. This institution performs economic, socializing, and ideological functions, crucial in the formation of gender identity, both subjectively and symbolically (Piedra Guillén 2013).

Authors such as Jelin (1994), Salles (1991), and García-Oliveira (1994) emphasize the importance of conceiving the family as a mediator between the individual and society, serving as a bridge between macro and micro social dimensions. This approach allows for an understanding of how changes in family structure affect subjectivities and social dynamics. In particular, the Foucauldian perspective (Foucault 2008) provides a deep critique of how the family constitutes itself as a regulatory axis of sexuality and power relations, reflecting and reinforcing social norms and expectations. Foucault argues that with the development of capitalism, the need to control bodies, and particularly people's sexuality, arose, with the family being the ideal space to exercise such control. Thus, changes in the family reflect a structural character, with traditional practices being questioned and impacting the social process.

Within the family, the exercise of parenting can be understood as a set of practices and responsibilities involving the care, education, and comprehensive development of children, transcending biology and blood ties (Butterfield & Padavic 2014). This exercise is built through continuous and meaningful interactions, prioritizing the emotional, social, and physical development of the child. Parenting, therefore, is not limited to the traditional family structure but encompasses diverse family configurations.

However, when it comes to LGBTQIA+ families, these parenting practices acquire an additional dimension due to specific challenges stemming from social expectations about the sexual orientation and gender identity of their members. Although the internal dynamics of

these families do not significantly differ from those of heterosexual cisgender families in aspects such as household task negotiation and conflict resolution, they face unique sociocultural obstacles such as limited support from state institutions and discrimination (Alday-Mondaca et al. 2024; Borneskog et al. 2014; Kurdek 2005, 2007).

Despite the lack of social and legal protection, LGBTQIA+ individuals continue to parent under adverse conditions (Alday-Mondaca et al. 2024; Alberdi & Mardones 2016; Díez 2015). Focusing the analysis on the emotions and affections that arise in the experience or possibility of exercising parenthood recognizes that these experiences are deeply influenced by the structures and social relationships in which they are embedded (Ariza 2016; Bericat 2016). Studies indicate that parenthood among LGBTQIA+ individuals is strengthened through deep emotional bonds and a genuine commitment to children's well-being, challenging traditional conceptions and creating safe and loving environments for children's development (Alday-Mondaca et al. 2024; Ariza 2016; Bericat 2016). We understand that emotions are fundamental parts of social and political interactions and must therefore be considered in studying LGBTQIA+ parenting, addressing the political dimension of affections and their relationship with the exercise and meaning of parenting (Ariza 2016; Liu 2020).

LGBTQIA+ parenting can take shape through children from previous heterosexual relationships, adoption, reproductive technologies, or planned co-parenting (Zambrano 2006). Garrafa's (2020) perspective on the adoption paradigm provides valuable contributions for understanding LGBTQIA+ parenting and the structuring of parental roles in contemporary times. Adoption, as a legal institution, allows the formation of non-biological parental bonds, regulated by the State to ensure a safe and loving environment for children. Schneider (2011) explores how parenting and family ties are culturally constructed, and Freeman (2010) challenges normative narratives by proposing queer temporalities that create space for alternative temporal experiences and challenge heteronormativity.

In the Chilean context, adoption legislation and the recent progress with the Equal Marriage Law (Law No. 21.400, 2021) reflect a progressive change in protecting LGBTQIA+ couples (Morrison 2022). However, these couples continue to face cultural challenges and prejudices

that affect their access to public policies related to assisted reproduction techniques and adoption (Fonasa 2020; Fraser 2011).

In Chile, the adoption process was managed by the National Service for Minors (SENAME) from 1980 until 2021, when the program focused exclusively on justice and juvenile reintegration under the Ministry of Justice and Human Rights. The service responsible for adopting children under 18 years old who have had their rights violated was renamed "Mejor Niñez" and is now under the Ministry of Social Development and Family (Sename 2021). The adoption program is defined as: "The set of activities aimed at providing the child with a responsible family, primarily including support and guidance to the child's family of origin, the child's reception and care, the technical evaluation of applicants, and their preparation as an adoptive family" (Sename 2018, p. 2).

Regarding same-sex couples living together, the responses given in May 2022 through the transparency portal indicate that Mejor Niñez states that the current legislation does not allow joint adoption, permitting only one partner to adopt, even though both are evaluated. This means that, under the existing law, in the absence of modifications to the adoption law, same-sex couples must dissolve their civil union agreement (if they have one) to initiate the process—as a single person—because the law requires a minimum of two years of marriage, or alternatively, the option to adopt as a single person within the mentioned hierarchical dynamic. In this latter case, although one member of the couple adopts, both will be evaluated "as they live together, both will be significant figures for the child." However, the legal bond of affiliation for the adopted child or adolescent will be established only with one of the cohabitants (Mejor Niñez 2022).

Therefore, this study aims to answer the following research question: *How do LGBTQIA+ families seeking to become parents through adoption construct their subjectivities amid power and resistance relationships within the existing regulatory and cultural framework?*

Analytical Development: Governmentality, Normalization, and Their Impact on LGBTQIA+ Parenting

Inspired by the discussion on Foucault's (1999) governmentality, this study examines how the Chilean State regulates the formation of families, with a particular focus on the inclusion of LGBTQIA+ couples. According to Foucault, one way to observe governmentality is through the regulation and supervision of adoptive families, influencing public perception and the self-subjectivation of adoptive families regarding new forms of parenting. Although the inclusion of LGBTQIA+ couples in the adoption process can be considered a step forward in terms of legal recognition in Chile, it is crucial to analyze the subtle forms of control and normalization that persist under this recognition.

Wendy Brown (2014) argues that commodification and individual responsibility are intertwined with social policies. In this neoliberal framework, the inclusion of LGBTQIA+ couples in the adoption field prioritizes efficiency and individual responsibility over substantive equality. This perspective suggests that despite the legal recognition of LGBTQIA+ couples' adoption rights, economic and social structures continue to perpetuate significant inequalities and limitations.

Butler (2011) provides a fundamental insight into how gender norms and performativity affect the recognition of LGBTQIA+ identities. Butler argues that gender categories and their associated norms are socially constructed and regulated, conditioning the recognition of LGBTQIA+ families according to dominant heteronormative norms that often exclude or marginalize these identities. This perspective illuminates how gender norms and expectations regarding parenting can influence how LGBTQIA+ families are perceived and accepted in the adoption context.

Michel Foucault (2007, 2008) offers a detailed analysis of the dynamics of power and regulation that shape the experiences of LGBTQIA+ families. According to Foucault, power manifests not only in explicit laws and policies but also in the discursive and normative practices that regulate sexuality and family relationships. In his understanding of governmentality, Foucault explores how state institutions and social practices exert control over bodies and identities through mechanisms of regulation and normalization. In the context of adoption, this means that although advances have been made in legalizing

LGBTQIA+ parenting, insidious forms of regulation and control continue to reflect and reinforce dominant social hierarchies and norms.

From these critical perspectives, it becomes clear that while the inclusion of LGBTQIA+ couples in the adoption process represents a significant step forward, structures and practices persist that limit true equality. Public policy reforms and the transformation of social norms must go beyond symbolic inclusion, aiming for social justice that addresses structural inequalities and mechanisms of control in the exercise of LGBTQIA+ parenting. Thus, this study seeks to understand the power and resistance relationships among LGBTQIA+ families seeking to become parents through adoption, analyzing how these families negotiate their identities and roles within the existing regulatory and cultural framework.

Methodology

For this objective, this study employs a qualitative approach, which, following Minayo's (2018) understanding, allows for the analysis of stories, relationships, representations, beliefs, perceptions, opinions, and interpretations that individuals have about their lives, artifacts, and themselves. This approach allows for uncovering social processes from the perspective of those involved, promoting spontaneity and the diversity of responses (Minayo 2018; Flick 2009).

Interviews were conducted with LGBTQIA+ families and state officials in Chile. The methodological procedures used included in-depth interviews, both individual and group, using a semi-structured guide. This technique aims to capture information expressed verbally, through gestures, body language, or the silences of interviewees (Gaínza Veloso 2006), providing depth to the communicative material for a detailed understanding of expressed meanings and senses.

Individual interviews were conducted with state professionals, while group interviews were held with "family nuclei," defined as couples or other relational configurations that self-identify as family. This group format facilitated collective knowledge construction from shared experiences, allowing for exploration of interactions among interviewees and a better understanding of the research subject.

The inclusion criteria were: LGBTQIA+ couples over 18 years old who identify as lesbomarental, homoparental, trans, or another type of family; as well as single-parent families; who have gone through the adoption process through the Chilean Public Adoption System (formerly SENAME) until 2021. Another selection criterion was the heterogeneity of the families in terms of their region of residence (macro-zones: north, center, and south).

Given the scarcity of studies on LGBTQIA+ families in Chile and the difficulty of access due to their dispersion, a subjective sampling based on a reasoned decision was chosen (Corbetta 2007). This strategy relied on the previous contacts of the principal investigator and their team with various LGBTQIA+ organizations in the country. This facilitated the identification and selection of participating families based on criteria of accessibility and regional diversity.

Data analysis was carried out using Critical Discourse Analysis, which allows for identifying the rules of discourse formation and exclusion, genealogies of discourse, and their historical implications (González-Domínguez & Martell-Gámez 2013). This approach was crucial for understanding how discursive practices shape the social context and subjectivities. Regarding ethical aspects, rigorous procedures were followed to protect the privacy and anonymity of participants, ensure confidentiality in handling information, obtain informed consent, and ensure voluntary participation without negative repercussions. These measures aimed to preserve the autonomy and well-being of those involved in the research (Agar 2004). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) and was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research on Human Subjects of the Faculty of Medicine at the University of Chile (Protocol No. 014-2022, Act No. 004; approved on April 19, 2022).

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Results

Table 1. Sociodemographic Data of Interviewed Families

Family	Composition	City	Years of Relationship	Years Living Together	Profession	No. of Children
F1	Homoparental	Santiago	16	14	Psychologist and University Professor	1 boy
F2	Homoparental	Santiago	20	17	Journalist and Agronomist	1 girl and 2 boys (biological siblings)
F3	Lesbomarental	La Serena	6	5	Social Workers	1 girl
F4	Homoparental	Santiago	10	5	Speech Therapist and Teacher	1 boy
F5	Homoparental	Santiago	11		Translator and Public Official	2 boys
F6	Lesbomarental	Santiago	15	10	Teacher and ??	1 boy

Source: Own elaboration.

According to the presented data, all interviewed families have members with higher education levels, suggesting a high or upper-middle socioeconomic level (Galobardes B et al. 2006). The adoptions range from one child to three biological siblings, highlighting the diversity and complexity of family dynamics within LGBTQIA+ families in Chile.

Table 2

Professional	Training	Position in Former SENAME
P1	Psychologist	Regional Adoption Team
P2	Social Worker	Technical Advisory

Source: Own elaboration.

The main results are presented below, grouped into categories that emerged from the critical discourse analysis. These categories were developed based on the identification of discursive rules, genealogies, and historical implications, and they are as follows:

Regulation and Normalization of Parenting

The interviewees' accounts of the adoption process reveal a complex scenario where evaluation and normalization practices play crucial roles. Through the psychosocial evaluation, not only is the aptitude of adoption candidates determined, but norms are also established regarding what constitutes an "adequate" family, including criteria for economic stability and conformity with established social norms. These practices reflect a mechanism of control that regulates the identities and perceived abilities of candidates as adoptive parents. As one of the interviewees observed:

"They asked for a criminal record certificate, passed psychometric tests, Rorschach tests, individual and group tests of both, drawing the tree under the rain. It was very thorough."
(F1)

"The bottom line is that since the program didn't work well in our case and given that we are in this legal uncertainty, we often have to undergo external scrutiny to effectively follow the procedure... a foster family is supposed to have a report sent to the judge every three or six months to confirm the family's competence, and it can be really exhausting at times." (F2)

Moreover, the interviews highlight how institutions like SENAME exert significant control over the adoption process. Lesbomarental and homoparental families, for example, face different norms and expectations compared to heterosexual families, reflecting asymmetries in institutional treatment.

Disciplinary processes such as psychometric tests and structured interviews are used to evaluate and categorize candidates, influencing not only their immediate actions but also their identities and perceived capabilities as adoptive parents. One participant shared their experience:

"It's like an unknown field. Throughout this entire process we've gone through, they've made us take many tests, many recorded sessions like bonding ones, and so on... it's been quite a journey. I think there might not be anyone who has had their parenthood so thoroughly evaluated as us because they keep asking us for reports all the time, like, if the kid drinks milk, if they don't, and if so, why, and if not, why not, and we have to attend sessions." (F1)

The hierarchies present in adoption priority categories and specific family requirements create divisions that privilege some individuals over others. This shows a disciplinary power that regulates who can adopt and under what conditions, shaping the possibilities for parenting according to legally established norms. Adoption in Chile is regulated by Law 19.620 of 1999, which prioritizes Chilean spouses as the first preference for placing a child for adoption. Second are married heterosexual foreigners with permanent residence in Chile. In both cases, couples are required to have been married for at least two years, a requirement that is waived if one or both have a medical infertility diagnosis. Lastly, Chilean singles, divorced, or widowed individuals who also must have permanent residency in Chile are considered (Norms on Child Adoption 1999).

"You have to analyze the other categories, and the Adoption Law identifies them by order of priority, or order of precedence, specifically, that's the term, and this order of precedence indicates who has the first priority, which are married Chileans, the second priority is married foreigners, and the third is widowed, single, and separated people. So in this order of precedence, we had to adopt as singles after nullifying the civil union agreement." (F2)

"The real discrimination was when they didn't let us be in the first priority for adoption because we weren't married... the law specifically states this order of precedence." (F1)

"And this order of operation, which relates to the third order of operation that today is in the adoption law reform pending in Congress for a couple of years, much more, and we worked

on that bill in the unit to address these issues. [...] Equality of conditions between civil marriage and single-parent families and leaving international families as the third or last resort." (P2)

"The bill that aims to equalize conditions is still in Congress. What happens today? Traditional families are indeed prioritized in court because that's how the law is structured, ultimately. Remember that family courts began to emerge after 2007, and this law is from '99. So, when the law talked about minors, it still referred to 'the minor'. The law then changed, and well, that's the only modification there is. [...] In 1999, this process changed to what we have today with the law. The law is certainly lacking. The law does not recognize—indeed, it does not recognize. In fact, the bill currently in Congress does not even recognize LGBTQIA+ families. Because there will continue to be family modalities, and the law or legal standard will never fully address a social fact." (P2)

The discussion extends beyond the simple evaluation of suitability, encompassing the formation of the family within an institutional context shaped by the State. State institutions and policies not only regulate but also shape the subjectivity of candidates and of the children available for adoption. This involves matters of sexuality and identity. By deciding who can adopt and how, the State not only oversees and controls the candidates' bodies but also influences who is considered 'adoptable'. Certain types of families are imagined as ideal, while others are subordinated on a scale where heterosexuality sits at the top or is even excluded from the process.

"We had to adopt as singles, which is in the third priority level... in sibling groups, especially trios or more, there are practically no families interested." (F2)

"We said, well, where are we going to compete with fewer interested parties, and in sibling groups, especially trios or larger groups, there are practically no families interested, so we thought the process could be faster and smoother that way, and indeed it was. [...] You have to go through a checklist of what you are willing to accept and what you're not, and it's a very explicit checklist: 'I'm willing to adopt a child who is the result of incest, a child who is the result of rape, a child with certain types of illnesses, yes to these illnesses, no to these

illnesses, a child with a disability in this degree, I'm willing to adopt a child with a moderate disability but not a severe one.' It had to be that explicit." (F3)

"Every year, there are about 500 families interested and 200 children declared adoptable, so one might say, well, if there are more families than children, they should all be matched, but that doesn't happen. And why not? Because most families are interested in adopting younger children, so what's missing is raising awareness of all these children who are waiting for a family but who, in reality, families are not willing to adopt because they are older. The average age is over 8 years. These things need to be made visible because probably that way, waiting times could be reduced. It's part of what we want to reform, part of what we want to change because for all I'm saying, you don't need laws; you need initiatives from the respective ministry, which is the Ministry of Social Development. So, is it a long process? No, it's not long; it's tedious, it's hostile, it's ungrateful, it's uncomfortable—all of that." (F2)

This dynamic of surveillance and control reflects existing social norms and contributes to constructing hierarchies and expectations that permeate the adoption process, profoundly affecting the experiences and shaping the construction of their subjectivities.

Hierarchies and Subjectivities in Adoption: The Paradox of Sensitivity and Marginalization of LGBTQIA+ Families

The discourses reveal various experiences and challenges faced by homoparental and lesboparental families during the adoption process. A recurring theme is the perception (both from officials and from the families themselves) that these families show a greater openness to adopting older children or those with special needs, challenging the established norms regarding the ideal profile of adoptive parents compared to the desires of heterosexual families. This willingness can be attributed to the unique life experience of LGBTQIA+ families, who, facing social and legal barriers, develop a special sensitivity to the needs of adopted children, thus challenging traditional paradigms about parenting.

However, while these narratives highlight positive aspects, they also conceal an underlying reality of unequal conditions and systemic discrimination. The State, by valuing LGBTQIA+

families for their sensitivity and willingness, perpetuates a narrative that obscures the barriers and control mechanisms imposed on these families.

"They are families that arrive or that are perceived to be much more sensitive than most families [...] so they have an openness to certain characteristics or variables that most families don't have, so their sensitivity impacts the expectation, where the imaginary of the child to be received is more flexible and broader—they expect much less, right?" (P1)

"The experience I've had with homoparental families has been the best I've seen and also the ones I've been able to assess positively because, personally, I've seen a sensitivity. [...] Well, personally, I've seen that male and female homoparental families have a different condition and are more sensitive. It also has to do with their own life story. It has to do with perhaps being more discriminated against or rejected because of their condition and having developed other strengths. From what I've seen in the suitability evaluation, their mentalization ability is super high. What I've seen is that their capacity for empathy is phenomenal." (P2)

"What SENAME says in these working groups, they have commented that the bonding experience with LGBT families is much more significant and faster because they claim that LGBT families have special skills due to their life stories that contribute to the bonding process and that particularly have to do with understanding the child's life story." (F2)

The perception that LGBTQIA+ families are more welcoming, although positive, also carries the contradiction that these same families are often invited to adopt children considered "difficult" to place. This scenario reveals a control mechanism that, while appearing to promote inclusion, reinforces structural inequality. The notion of normalization is evident, where certain families are considered ideal for caring for vulnerable children, while others are marginalized or used to address specific system challenges.

"It is undeniable that, due to the greater sensitivity of homoparental families, they are matched with children who might otherwise not have found a family—it is undeniable; we couldn't say otherwise." (P1)

"For us, the greatest strength of homoparental families is that... I have three... I always talk about people as if they were mine, but it's just a habit. I have three families that took in three siblings, and those three siblings were very difficult to place because three children at once is challenging. Generally, they have very different ages, as I mentioned before. We have a family that adopted a little girl who has Down syndrome and HIV, a trans girl, another child with cognitive disabilities. Generally, those who are placed with sibling groups have many personal resources, but the fact that there are three is what makes it challenging. So, I would say that generally, the greatest strength of homoparental families is that they have been a real option for children who would have been difficult to find families for, and the breakdown rate or failed processes is lower compared to the breakdown rates for heterosexual families—it's much lower." (P1)

However, this "choice" is often a response to the marginalized position they occupy within the adoption system, revealing how biopower operates disguised as good intentions.

"I think it starts from a place with fewer prejudices about anything, in general, like this idea that heterosexual families are looking for a very specific type of child to adopt—young, a single child. That creates these limitations on forming bonds with other types of children who don't fit into everything that is sought after. [...] And that is because of two reasons: LGBTQ families tend to be open to adopting a broader spectrum of children in all their diversity, whether physical, cognitive, or emotional. And this is due to, as I said, two reasons: one has to do with the order of precedence, as singles, we were in third priority, so before equal marriage, the tendency was for LGBTQ families to consider a wider range of children because that way, they had better chances of success in achieving adoption." (F2)

The experiences narrated by former SENAME workers and homoparental and lesbomarental families show how the disposition of LGBTQIA+ families to adopt a broader spectrum of children due to their lower priority ranking also leads them to face specific barriers and prejudices. By being more flexible, these families challenge traditional limitations and seek to be part of the solution for children who otherwise would have few opportunities to be adopted. However, this "choice" often stems from the marginalization they face within the adoption system.

Discussion

The discussion on LGBTQIA+ families in the adoption process in Chile can be understood through the lens of governmentality (Foucault 2008), identifying how the State exercises power through the regulation of individual and collective behaviors. In this sense, power is manifested not only in practices of normalization and social control but also in how state policies shape identities and subjectivities, especially under a neoliberal logic that perpetuates the structural marginalization of LGBTQIA+ families while simultaneously responding to gaps in the adoption system that heterosexual couples do not fulfill. The expectations and desires of heterosexual couples, as reported by public officials, are more limited and oriented toward an ideal of a neoliberal family. This is corroborated by another study conducted in Chile, which analyzed the "Chile Crece Contigo" program and revealed how gender stereotypes supported by heteronormative models produced the marginalization of a significant percentage of families that do not fit the public policy imaginary under these models. This structural marginalization operates by privileging certain lifestyles and family compositions that align with hegemonic and heteronormative values, contributing to the invisibility of LGBTQIA+ families (Morrison Gallardo Fuster 2023).

The normative structure of the former SENAME and Chile's adoption legislation exemplify how heteronormativity and patriarchy influence the regulation of adoption, as described in other studies on the heteronormative representations of the public system in Chile (Morrison Gallardo Fuster 2023; Morrison Moreno et al. 2023). Law 19.620 of 1999, which prioritized married couples and relegated singles and LGBTQIA+ families, demonstrates a legal hierarchy that favors traditional families (Sename 2018). This regulation shows an enunciative structure that perpetuates the hegemony of traditional families while marginalizing other forms of family constitution. As Morrison (2022) argues, the impact of ideological, religious, and moral premises on family regulation is significant, as these premises reinforce a normative view that not only sustains the superiority of the traditional family but also excludes and devalues alternative family configurations. This effect is amplified by the implementation of laws that, while aiming to address discrimination, end up reinforcing the heteronormative and religiously based logic, maintaining the marginalization of families that do not conform to hegemonic patterns.

According to Gayle Rubin (2007), the discourses on LGBTQIA+ families reveal how privilege and marginalization are deeply intertwined in the context of the adoption process. Rubin argues that social and legal norms categorize and hierarchize sexual and family identities, creating systems of privilege that benefit some groups while marginalizing others. In the context of adoption, this dynamic is clearly manifested when LGBTQIA+ families are classified in a third priority order for adoption. This system of precedence places LGBTQIA+ families at the bottom of the recognition and privilege pyramid, perpetuating their marginalization and highlighting the need for a critical reassessment of adoption policies to achieve greater equity and social justice.

The analysis reveals that while LGBTQIA+ families are praised for their willingness to adopt older children or those with special needs, this willingness largely responds to their marginalized position within the adoption system. The State, by valuing these families for their sensitivity and openness, perpetuates a narrative that conceals the barriers and control mechanisms they face. The recognition of LGBTQIA+ families as more empathetic and open is positive for their identity as families but masks a reality of structural inequality. The State, in promoting the inclusion of these families, reinforces inequality by relegating them to adopting children considered "difficult." This dynamic reflects the biopower described by Foucault, where apparent inclusion becomes a mechanism of control that perpetuates marginalization (Foucault 2008).

The concept of governmentality is crucial to understanding how the State, under the guise of neutrality and "good intentions," implements policies that, while seemingly inclusive, reinforce and reproduce inequalities (Foucault 2008). According to the study by Morrison Moreno et al. (2023), by analyzing official documents from Mejor Niñez, it is understood how governmentality is also expressed from a heteronormative position that affects the organization of individuals, especially concerning the understanding of LGBTQIA+ individuals as belonging to a different level of rights and thus as people of lesser value. The representations that emerge from the gaps in public policies, conceived from heteronormative logics, constitute subjects who seem incomprehensible, even when laws explicitly name them.

LGBTQIA+ families are often subjected to additional scrutiny, such as more exhaustive psychometric tests, more frequent and detailed interviews, and ongoing evaluations that question their suitability as parents. They may also be required to demonstrate their economic, emotional, and social stability more explicitly, as well as their ability to provide an "appropriate" environment for children's development, all from a perspective that often assumes the superiority of heteronormative family models. These processes can include more intrusive questionnaires about their personal lives and family dynamics, as well as more intense surveillance by the institutions responsible for the adoption process, reflecting a logic of power. Thus, although the issue of filiation in LGBTQIA+ families may be considered by the State, the practical operation of this norm is restricted by another set of norms that limit it, revealing the tactical polyvalence of discourses in Foucauldian terms. It is evident how forms of power diversify in attempts to maintain a determined order from different perspectives.

Neoliberalism, as noted by Fraser (2013), promotes a superficial version of inclusion that does not challenge the underlying power structures. In the case of LGBTQIA+ families in the adoption process, this apparent inclusion is implemented based on criteria that reinforce existing structural inequalities. Firstly, they are required to demonstrate their ability to conform to normative expectations of parenting, expectations that are deeply rooted in heteronormative ideals.

Fraser (2013) emphasizes how neoliberalism has co-opted feminist struggles and other social justice movements, promoting a superficial version of inclusion that does not challenge underlying power structures. This is evident in the adoption process for LGBTQIA+ families, where supposedly inclusive policies merely reinforce structural inequalities. By requiring LGBTQIA+ families to conform to traditional family models, the neoliberal State fails to recognize the diversity of family configurations and uses these families as a resource to meet adoption system demands without offering them the same guarantees and rights as heteronormative families.

Moreover, neoliberalism tends to commodify adoption, where children and families are treated as elements in a market. Here, LGBTQIA+ families are seen as a "resource" to meet

the demand for homes for children in the adoption system but are marginalized by not being considered "ideal consumers" in this market, especially for children under the age of four.

The analysis of the adoption process for LGBTQIA+ families in Chile reveals how neoliberal policies and underlying power structures perpetuate marginalization. Through governmentality, the State not only regulates and normalizes behaviors but also uses a façade of inclusion to mask practices that reinforce structural inequalities. It is imperative, therefore, to critically reevaluate these policies to dismantle inherent hierarchies and advance towards a more equitable and genuine social justice that recognizes and respects the diversity of family configurations without resorting to control mechanisms that perpetuate exclusion.

Final Reflections

The analysis of adoption practices in Chile, framed within the categories of regulation and normalization of parenting practices and the hierarchies and subjectivities in adoption, reveals a series of complex dynamics operating under the lens of governmentality and power.

The regulation of the adoption process in Chile illustrates how institutional norms and practices not only aim to ensure the suitability of adoptive parents but also reflect and reinforce a normative vision of the family. The rigorous process of psychosocial evaluation, along with the priority criteria established by Law 19.620, evidences a structure that favors heterosexual families and married couples, relegating single people and LGBTQIA+ families to a secondary position in the adoption hierarchy. This relentless need to meet specific criteria, such as economic stability and alignment with social norms, reveals how adoption is intertwined with normative ideals that perpetuate the hegemony of the traditional family.

This process reflects a dynamic of power where inclusion is intertwined with control. By imposing strict and specific standards, the adoption system not only regulates the practice of parenting but also contributes to the construction of social and family hierarchies embedded in legislation and everyday practice. The apparent inclusion of LGBTQIA+ families can, in fact, consolidate their marginalization by positioning them as a solution to specific system challenges, thus reinforcing their subordinate position in the adoption order of precedence.

In terms of subjectivation processes, the relationship between LGBTQIA+ individuals and the Chilean State is marked by a complex interplay between formal acceptance and practical marginalization. Public policies, while sometimes appearing to be inclusive, often operate under a logic that perpetuates structural hierarchies and inequalities. The processes of subjectivation for LGBTQIA+ individuals in this context are shaped by how the State regulates and validates their experiences, thus shaping their possibilities for forming families. In this sense, the Chilean State, by imposing evaluation criteria and specific requirements for adoption, not only regulates parenting practices but also contributes to constructing and limiting the subjectivity of these individuals within a heteronormative framework.

The subjectivation of LGBTQIA+ individuals in relation to the Chilean State is expressed in how these individuals must adapt to normative expectations to obtain recognition and legitimacy. This adaptation may involve an internalization of predominant values and a reconfiguration of roles to meet the established standards.

The recognition of the sensitivity of LGBTQIA+ families and their willingness to adopt children with special needs, rather than representing a true openness of the system, may actually consolidate their marginalization. These families are viewed as a solution to specific system problems, but this "choice" is deeply influenced by their subordinate position in the adoption order of precedence.

Achieving true social inclusion requires implementing legislative and cultural changes in practices and attitudes toward adoption. This means promoting greater visibility and acceptance of different family configurations in the media, education, and professional practices. Awareness and education about family diversity must be a priority to overcome the prejudices and stereotypes that persist in society.

In the context of adoption, this means recognizing and valuing all forms of family, not only in theory but also in daily practice. Mechanisms must be established to ensure that all families have the opportunity to demonstrate their suitability and are provided with the necessary tools for success in the adoption process. Inclusion also involves creating an environment where all families feel equally accepted and valued, regardless of their composition or structure.

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